

Contextually Relevant Computing Education Materials for Africa

Activity Catalog

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Summary

Each example will have the following fields to describe them:

- The CS1 Learning Outcomes (LOs) covered
- The primary CS concepts being taught (e.g., iteration, functions with parameters, file I/O, etc.)
- The type of problem (e.g., debugging, code tracing, problem solving, etc.)
- The cultural elements the authors aimed to tap into (e.g., dress, cuisine, lifestyle, etc.)

These will be followed by a problem description and, where appropriate and convenient, a model solution.

Botswana

Explore Botswana's Tribes and Languages

CS1 LOs	Develop programs that use the fundamental programming constructs: assignment and expressions, basic I/O, conditional and iterative statements. Develop programs using functions with parameter passing. Develop programs that effectively use the different structured data types provided in the language like arrays/lists, dictionaries, and sets.
CS Concepts	Iteration, conditionals, functions, built-in data structures (list, dictionary), user I/O
Problem Type	Programming problem solving
Cultural Elements	Lifestyle (Languages and tribes)

Description:

Write a program that helps users explore the languages and tribes of Botswana and their places of origin. The program should allow users to input a tribe's name and then output information about the language they speak and the place they originate from. Additionally, the program should be able to list all tribes along with their languages and places of origin.

Model Solution (Python):

```
tribes_data =
[
{"tribe": "Bakwena", "language": "Sekwena", "origin": "Kweneng"},
{"tribe": "Balete", "language": "Selete", "origin": "South Eastern Botswana"},
{"tribe": "Bangwato", "language": "Sengwato", "origin": "Central Botswana"},
{"tribe": "Bakalaka", "language": "Sekalaka", "origin": "North Botswana"},
]

def display_all_tribes():
    print("Tribes of Botswana:")
    for tribe in tribes_data:
        print(f"Tribe: {tribe['tribe']}, Language: {tribe['language']},
              Origin: {tribe['origin']}")

def search_tribe(tribe_name):
    for tribe in tribes_data:
        if tribe["tribe"].lower() == tribe_name.lower():
            print(f"The {tribe['tribe']} tribe speaks {tribe['language']})
```

```

        and originates from {tribe['origin']}.)")
    return
    print("Tribe not found.")

while True:
    print("\n1. Display all tribes\n2. Search for a tribe by name\n3. Exit")
    choice = input("Enter your choice: ")

    if choice == "1":
        display_all_tribes()
    elif choice == "2":
        tribe_name = input("Enter the name of the tribe: ")
        search_tribe(tribe_name)
    elif choice == "3":
        print("Goodbye!")
        Break
    else:
        print("Invalid choice. Please try again.")

```

Simulating Traditional Dance Moves

CS1 LOs	Develop programs that use the fundamental programming constructs: assignment and expressions, basic I/O, conditional and iterative statements.
CS Concepts	Iteration, conditionals, built-in data structures (list, dictionary)
Problem Type	Problem Solving
Cultural Elements	Dance

Description:

In Botswana, traditional dances like the Setapa Dance are performed in response to specific drum beats. Different beats correspond to different dance moves. By simulating this, students can learn how to use programming constructs to map inputs (drum beats) to outputs (dance moves). Create a simple Python program that simulates traditional dance moves based on a sequence of drum beats. This exercise will help students understand basic programming concepts such as lists, dictionaries, loops, and conditional statements.

Model Solution (Python):

```

drum_beats = ["beat1", "beat2", "beat3", "beat1"]
dance_moves = {
    "beat1": "Step Left",
    "beat2": "Step Right",
    "beat3": "Jump"
}

```

```

}
for beat in drum_beats:
    if beat in dance_moves:
        print(f"Drum beat: {beat} -> Dance move: {dance_moves[beat]}")
    else:
        print(f"Drum beat: {beat} -> Dance move: Unknown")

```

Deconstructing Poetry

CS1 LOs	Develop programs that effectively use the different structured data types provided in the language like arrays/lists, dictionaries, and sets. Read a given program and explain what it does.
CS Concepts	Iteration, built-in data structures (list)
Problem Type	Code comprehension
Cultural Elements	Media (Poems)

Description:

Explain what each line of code does in the program below. What is the output of the overall program? How can you modify it to print only the first words "Naledi e le"?

```

leboko= [
    "Naledi e le,",
    "Ya mariberibe, ribela ka pele,",
    "Re ye go nwa metsi,",
    "Metsi ga a yo,",
    "A nolwe ke Kgaupe,",
    "Kgaupe ga ke morate,",
    "Ke rata Masilonyana."
]

for line in leboko:
    print(line)

```

Nigeria

Validating drum sequence

CS1 LOs	Develop programs that use the fundamental programming constructs: assignment and expressions, basic I/O, conditional and iterative statements. Develop programs using functions with parameter passing. Develop programs that effectively use the different structured data types provided in the language like arrays/lists, dictionaries, and sets.
CS Concepts	Iteration, built-in data structures (list), conditionals, functions
Problem Type	Problem Solving
Cultural Elements	Music (Talking Drum - Dundun)

Description:

A specific rhythm must be followed in Nigerian traditional drumming, especially in talking drum (dundun) ensembles. If the rhythm goes off, it's akin to having a bug in your code. Debugging in this context would involve identifying the drummer who missed a beat or played incorrectly and correcting their pattern to restore the intended rhythm.

Write a Python program to determine if a given drum pattern follows a specific rhythm. The correct rhythm pattern is a repeating sequence of "boom," "clap," and "snap" in that exact order. Specifically, a "boom" should always be followed by a "clap," and a "clap" should always be followed by a "snap."

Model Solution (Python):

```
def is_correct_rhythm(drum_pattern):
    # Define the correct sequence pattern
    correct_sequence = ["boom", "clap", "snap"]
    correct_sequence_index = 0

    for beat in drum_pattern:
        # Check if the beat matches the expected beat in the sequence
        if beat == correct_sequence[correct_sequence_index]:
            # Move to the next beat in the sequence
            correct_sequence_index = (correct_sequence_index + 1) %
                len(correct_sequence)
        else:
            # If the beat doesn't match the expected beat, the rhythm is
            incorrect
    return False
```

```

    return True

# Example drum patterns
drum_pattern1 = ["boom", "clap", "snap", "boom", "clap", "snap"]
drum_pattern2 = ["boom", "boom", "clap", "boom", "clap", "boom"]

print(is_correct_rhythm(drum_pattern1)) # Output: True
print(is_correct_rhythm(drum_pattern2)) # Output: False

```

Debugging the cooking process

CS1 LOs	Trace the flow of control during the execution of a program.
CS Concepts	State change, Functions, User input/output
Problem Type	Code tracing, Debugging
Cultural Elements	Cuisine

Description:

The following code simulates the process of making iyan (pounded yam). However, there are subtle errors in the sequence of steps that lead to incorrect preparation of the yam. Your task is to identify and correct the mistakes.

```

def prepare_iyan(yam):
    print("Peeling the yam...")
    temp = "peeled " + yam

    print("Boiling the yam until tender...")
    temp = "tender " + yam

    print("Cutting the yam into pieces...")
    temp = "pieces of " + temp

    print("Pounding the yam...")
    temp = "pounded " + yam

    print("Mixing and smoothing with hot water...")
    yam = "smooth " + temp

    print("Iyan is ready:", temp)
    return temp

raw_yam = "raw yam"

```

```
iyan = prepare_iyan(raw_yam)
```

Model Solution:

```
def prepare_iyan(yam):  
    print("Peeling the yam...")  
    temp = "peeled " + yam  
  
    print("Cutting the yam into pieces...")  
    temp = "pieces of " + temp  
  
    print("Boiling the yam until tender...")  
    temp = "tender " + temp  
  
    print("Pounding the yam...")  
    temp = "pounded " + temp  
  
    print("Mixing and smoothing with hot water...")  
    temp = "smooth " + temp  
  
    print("Iyan is ready:", temp)  
    return temp  
  
raw_yam = "raw yam"  
  
iyan = prepare_iyan(raw_yam)
```

Royal Greeting Merge

CS1 LOs	Develop programs that use the fundamental programming constructs: assignment and expressions, basic I/O, conditional and iterative statements. Develop programs using functions with parameter passing. Develop programs that use file I/O to provide data persistence across multiple executions
CS Concepts	Iteration, conditionals, file I/O, error handling, functions
Problem Type	Problem Solving
Cultural Elements	Government, Social Customs , Royalty Poetry

Description:

An Oriki is a form of praise poetry in Yoruba culture, often used to honor individuals, deities, or towns. These poems celebrate the subject's achievements, qualities, and lineage. They are

traditionally recited during various ceremonies and significant events, using a call-and-response structure to engage the audience and enhance the communal experience.

You are tasked with creating a program that reads a call-and-response Oriki from two separate files, merges them into a single file, and adds the labels "Call" and "Response" before each line as necessary. There should be an equal number of calls and responses.

call.txt

```
The king with authority, second only to the gods!  
The king who lives in a palace with an indigo roof!  
The glorious king who resides in his city!
```

response.txt

```
Authority, second only to the gods!  
Palace with an indigo roof!  
The king who resides in his city!
```

Model Solution (Python):

```
def read_lines(file_path):  
    with open(file_path, 'r', encoding='utf-8') as file:  
        return [line.strip() for line in file.readlines()]  
  
def save_oriki(file_path, oriki_lines):  
    with open(file_path, 'w', encoding='utf-8') as file:  
        for line in oriki_lines:  
            file.write(line + '\n')  
  
def merge_call_response(calls, responses):  
    if len(calls) != len(responses):  
        raise ValueError("The number of calls and responses must be equal.")  
  
    merged_oriki = []  
    for call, response in zip(calls, responses):  
        merged_oriki.append(f"Call: {call}")  
        merged_oriki.append(f"Response: {response}")  
    return merged_oriki  
  
def main():  
    # Step 1: Read calls and responses from files  
    calls = read_lines('call.txt')  
    responses = read_lines('response.txt')  
  
    # Step 2: Merge calls and responses with labels  
    merged_oriki = merge_call_response(calls, responses)
```

```

# Step 3: Save the merged Oriki to a file
save_oriki('oriki_output.txt', merged_oriki)

if __name__ == "__main__":
    main()

```

Using Dictionaries to Store the Society Structure

CS1 LOs	Develop programs that effectively use the different structured data types provided in the language like arrays/lists, dictionaries, and sets.
CS Concepts	Built-in data structures (list, dictionary)
Problem Type	Problem Solving
Cultural Elements	Social Customs, Government

Description:

In Fulani culture, the hierarchical structure of a clan is crucial for maintaining social order and cultural traditions. Each clan member has a specific role and responsibilities within the clan.

Your task is to create a hierarchical structure representing a Fulani clan using dictionaries and tuples in Python. Define a nested dictionary to represent the hierarchical structure of a Fulani clan. Each clan member should have a **name**, **role**, and a list of **children** representing their subordinates.

Clan Head (Arđo Usman)

Model Solution (Python):

```

fulani_clan = {
    "name": "Arđo Usman",
    "role": "Clan Head",
    "children": [
        {
            "name": "Ibrahim",

```


Printing Societal Structure

CS1 LOs	Develop programs that effectively use the different structured data types provided in the language like arrays/lists, dictionaries, and sets.
CS Concepts	Iteration, built-in data structures, functions, recursion
Problem Type	Programming problem solving
Cultural Elements	Social Customs, Governance

Description:

Understanding the hierarchical structure of a Fulani clan is easier when it is visually represented. Your task is to create a function that prints the hierarchical structure in an indented format, making it clear which members report to whom.

Write a function `print_clan()` that takes the hierarchical dictionary created in [the previous problem](#) and prints the structure. The function should recursively print each member's name and role, with indentation representing the hierarchy levels.

Your function should meet the following requirements:

- The root member (Clan Head) should have no indentation.
- Each level of the hierarchy should be indented with two spaces more than the previous level.
- It should use the data structure from the [previous problem](#)

Model Solution (Python):

```
def print_clan(member, level=0):
    indent = "  " * level
    print(f"{indent}{member['name']} ({member['role']})")
    for child in member["children"]:
        print_clan(child, level + 1)

# Example usage
print("Hierarchical Structure of the Fulani Clan:")
print_clan(fulani_clan)
```

South Africa

Calculating Tin Cans for a Pyramid in Three Toti

CS1 LOs	Develop programs that use the fundamental programming constructs: assignment and expressions, basic I/O, conditional and iterative statements.
CS Concepts	Iteration
Problem Type	Problem Solving
Cultural Elements	Game

Description:

You and your friends would like to play a game of *Three toti*. They are struggling to determine how many tin cans they require to build a pyramid of tin cans. Write an algorithm, in the language of your choice, to determine how many tin cans are needed to stack on top of one another when the base number of tin cans are provided. The following provides an illustration of how the tin cans are stacked.

Model Solution (Python):

```
# Algorithm:
# line = base - 1, sum = sum + line until line == 1

base = 5
line = base
sum = base

while line > 1:
    line = line - 1
```

```

sum = sum + line
print(sum)

```

Simulating the Game of Jukskei

CS1 LOs	Develop programs that use the fundamental programming constructs: assignment and expressions, basic I/O, conditional and iterative statements. Develop programs using functions with parameter passing. Develop programs that effectively use the different structured data types provided in the language like arrays/lists, dictionaries, and sets.
CS Concepts	Dynamic arrays, functions, conditionals, iteration
Problem Type	Problem Solving
Cultural Elements	Game

Description:

The game of *Jukskei* requires you to throw the *skei* as close to the peg (*juk*) as possible from a distance of 10 to 16 meters. A *skei* can be anything that will not roll (for example a bowling pin) from where it lands in the sand strip into which the peg has been placed. You may assume that there are 2 teams of 4 members each and each team member gets 2 *skei*'s each. Each team takes turns in throwing their *skei*. The team with the most *skei*'s closest to the peg get that number added to their score. If a team member knocks over the peg, they automatically get 3 points for their team. The team that reaches exactly 23 points first, wins the game. If a team exceed 23 points in a round, their score is zero'ed.

Designing an Inventory System for a Food Stand Using C++

CS1 LOs	Develop programs that effectively use the different structured data types provided in the language like arrays/lists, dictionaries, and sets.
CS Concepts	Dynamic Arrays, structures, object orientations?
Problem Type	Problem solving
Cultural Elements	Cuisine

Description:

A friend of yours has decided to open a food stand. To help them manage their daily stock, they have asked you to write an inventory system for them. Each item will be given a name, for example Babotie, a price and the stock available for the day. This information will be stored in a

C++ struct. Items will be categorised. Categories may include, Snacks, Meals, Desserts, etc. Design a structure using Dynamic Arrays and C++ structs to model a menu for the food stand. Show how you will insert food items into the structure and how you will change the available quantities as the day progresses and items are sold. To keep the menu up to date, you may assume your friend has a screen and only projects on the screen the items that are still in stock. For inspiration as to what to put on the menu, look at:
<https://cheflolaskitchen.com/delicious-south-african-foods/>

Egypt

Trace the output of Koshari ingredients

CS1 LOs	Trace the flow of control during the execution of a program.
CS Concepts	Iteration, basic data structures
Problem Type	Code tracing
Cultural Elements	Cuisine

Description:

Trace the following code and write down the output:

```
# List of ingredients in Koshari
koshari_ingredients = ["Rice", "Lentils", "Chickpeas", "Pasta", "Onions",
    "Garlic", "Tomato Sauce", "Vinegar", "Spices (cumin, coriander)", "Fried
    Onions (optional topping)"]

# Iterating through the list of Koshari ingredients
print("Ingredients for making Koshari:")
for ingredient in koshari_ingredients:
    print("- " + ingredient)
```

Trace the output of traditional Egyptian clothing items

CS1 LOs	Trace the flow of control during the execution of a program.
CS Concepts	Iteration, built-in data structures
Problem Type	Code tracing
Cultural Elements	Dress

Description:

Trace the following code and write down the output:

```
# List of traditional clothing items in Egyptian culture defined in one line
egyptian_clothing = ["Galabeya", "Tarboosh (Fez)", "Abaya", "Kaffiyeh",
    "Jellabiya", "Shawl (Refaa)", "Turban (Imamah)", "Baladi Dress",
    "Taqiyah", "Hijab", "Niqab"]
```

```

# Using a for loop to iterate through the list of clothing items
print("Traditional clothing items in Egyptian culture and their significance:")
for item in egyptian_clothing:
    print(f"- {item}")

# Displaying a message after the loop
print("These clothing items reflect the rich cultural heritage and traditions of
      Egypt.")

```

Outputting hand-made embroidery textiles

CS1 LOs	Develop programs that use the fundamental programming constructs: assignment and expressions, basic I/O, conditional and iterative statements. Develop programs that effectively use the different structured data types provided in the language like arrays/lists, dictionaries, and sets.
CS Concepts	Iteration, built-in data structures, user I/O
Problem Type	Programming problem solving
Cultural Elements	Dress

Description:

Write a program to provide the user with descriptions of several types of hand-made embroidery found in Luxor and Aswan. Utilise the following dictionary in your solution:

```

embroidered_textiles = {
    "Galabeya Embroidery": "Traditional Egyptian dress embroidery, often
        featuring vibrant colors and intricate patterns.",
    "Tally Embroidery": "Embroidery style characterized by geometric motifs and
        often used in traditional Nubian clothing.",
    "Khayamiya": "Tentmaker's appliqué, known for its decorative textile panels
        used traditionally for tents, now also seen in wall hangings and
        other decorative items.",
    "Nubian Embroidery": "Embroidery style originating from Nubia, often
        featuring bold designs and bright colors.",
    "Abaya Embroidery": "Embroidery commonly found on women's abayas (loose
        overgarments) in the region, showcasing delicate and intricate
        patterns.",
    "Shawl Embroidery": "Embroidery embellishments often found on shawls,
        scarves, and wraps, adding a touch of elegance to these garments.",
}

```

```

        "Headscarf Embroidery": "Embroidery on headscarves, representing cultural
                                identity and often passed down through generations."
    }

```

Model Solution (Python):

```

# Basic I/O: Asking user for input
print("Welcome to the Luxor and Aswan Embroidered Textiles Guide!")
print("Choose a type of embroidered textile to learn more:")
for idx, textile in enumerate(embroidered_textiles.keys(), start=1):
    print(f"{idx}. {textile}")
choice = int(input("Enter the number corresponding to your choice: "))

# Conditional statements based on user input
if 1 <= choice <= len(embroidered_textiles):
    selected_textile = list(embroidered_textiles.keys())[choice - 1]
    print(f"You chose {selected_textile}:")
    print(embroidered_textiles[selected_textile])
else:
    print("Invalid choice! Please select a number within the provided range.")

```

Printing a pyramid

CS1 LOs	Develop programs that use the fundamental programming constructs: assignment and expressions, basic I/O, conditional and iterative statements. Develop programs using functions with parameter passing.
CS Concepts	Iteration, conditionals, functions with parameters
Problem Type	Programming problem solving
Cultural Elements	Housing

Description:

Iterate through the layers of the pyramid and print out each layer as it's being built. Your program should simulate building a pyramid with a specified number of layers. Each layer will be represented by a series of asterisks (*) to visualize the pyramid's structure.

You should define a function `build_pyramid(layers)` that takes the number of layers as input. Within the function, use a loop to iterate through each layer of the pyramid.

For each layer, first print the necessary spaces to center the layer horizontally, and then print the asterisks (*) to represent the layer.

Here is some sample output with a height of 5:

```
  *
 * *
* * *
* * * *
* * * * *
```

Model Solution (Python):

```
def build_pyramid(layers):
    for i in range(1, layers + 1):
        # Print spaces before the asterisks to center the pyramid
        print(" " * (layers - i), end="")
        # Printing asterisks for the current layer
        print("* " * i)

# Number of layers in the pyramid
num_layers = 5

# Building the pyramid with the specified number of layers
build_pyramid(num_layers)
```

List Egyptian football players

CS1 LOs	Develop programs that use the fundamental programming constructs: assignment and expressions, basic I/O, conditional and iterative statements. Develop programs that effectively use the different structured data types provided in the language like arrays/lists, dictionaries, and sets.
CS Concepts	Iteration, built-in data structures
Problem Type	Programming problem solving
Cultural Elements	Sport

Description:

Create a program that iterates through a list of famous Egyptian football players and prints out their names along with some key information, such as their position and achievements. This will involve basic iteration through a list and displaying relevant information.

You should create a list of `egyptian_football_players` containing dictionaries for each player, with keys for their `name`, `position`, `club`, and `achievements`.

You should use a for loop to iterate through each player in the list. Within the loop, we print out the player's name, position, club, and achievements.

You can expand this program by adding more players to the list and including additional information about each player if desired.

Model Solution (Python):

```
# List of famous Egyptian football players
egyptian_football_players = [
    {"name": "Mohamed Salah", "position": "Forward", "club": "Liverpool",
     "achievements": "Premier League Golden Boot winner (2017-2018,
     2018-2019)"},
    {"name": "Ahmed Hegazi", "position": "Defender", "club": "Al-Ittihad",
     "achievements": "African Cup of Nations winner (2010)"},
    {"name": "Mohamed Aboutrika", "position": "Midfielder", "club": "Retired",
     "achievements": "African Cup of Nations winner (2006, 2008, 2010)}
]

# Iterating through the list of football players
print("Famous Egyptian Football Players:")
for player in egyptian_football_players:
    print(f>Name: {player['name']}")
    print(f>Position: {player['position']}")
    print(f>Club: {player['club']}")
    print(f>Achievements: {player['achievements']}")
    print()
```

Zambia

Create an ichienga stones game simulation

CS1 LOs	Develop programs that use the fundamental programming constructs: assignment and expressions, basic I/O, conditional and iterative statements.
CS Concepts	Iteration, basic user I/O, conditionals
Problem Type	Programming problem solving
Cultural Elements	Game

Description:

Write a program to simulate a game of ichienga. In ichienga, you will have a number of stones in a circle. You toss a large stone in the air and sweep out any number of stones you like. Then you must toss the large stone again and sweep in all but one of the stones.

Your program should:

- Prompt the player for the number of stones they would like to sweep out
- Perform the sweep out computationally
- Perform the sweep in computationally
- If successful, the program should repeat the steps of the game until the circle is empty

Establish a magic number which is the easiest number of stones to move in one sweep; e.g., 6. The sweep computation should then increase the chance of failure the further the number selection is from 6. E.g., if the player chooses to sweep out 6 itself, the probability of failure will be very low (but not zero, because they may fumble their stone toss). However, for the sweep in, they then have no choice but to sweep in 5 stones, so the probability of failure will be higher. The probability of failure will increase as they progress in the game as eventually there will be too few stones to always sweep out 6.

As an extension, you could add a random chance that the player fails to sweep the exact number of stones they indicate, since there is dexterity required in the motion. You could also increase the chance of a mis-sweep if there are more stones in the circle (since it is harder to be precise when trying to sweep a set number of stones from a larger mass).

Create an object-oriented mobile network account simulation

CS1 LOs	Develop programs that use the fundamental programming constructs: assignment and expressions, basic I/O, conditional and iterative statements.
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	Develop programs using functions with parameter passing. Develop programs that create simple classes and instantiate objects of those classes (if supported by the language).
CS Concepts	Object Orientation, methods with parameters
Problem Type	Programming problem solving
Cultural Elements	Lifestyle/Communication

Description:

You are to design an object-oriented version of a cell phone account manager for a new cell phone network. The main class to develop is a phone record, which should have the following instance variables:

- A phone number (should this be an integer or a string?)
- A name associated with the phone record
- A value for the airtime balance of the account

Your class should also have several methods for the following tasks:

- Make a text, which should cost a fixed amount of airtime
- Make a phone call, which will cost a variable amount of airtime depending on the length of the call
- Top up airtime, which should increase the airtime on the account by a fixed amount
- Share airtime, which should reduce the balance of the instanced account and increase the balance of another account

Include reasonable error checking and resolution according to your own judgment (e.g., if a call is made which is too long, how will your program react? Will the airtime be in negative balance or will the balance be reduced to zero with an error message to indicate that they would have been cut off early?)

Once you have completed your class, create a few instances and demonstrate the working program by having them perform some of the functionality.

Design a citenge with Turtle graphics

CS1 LOs	Develop programs that use the fundamental programming constructs: assignment and expressions, basic I/O, conditional and iterative statements. Develop programs using functions with parameter passing.
CS Concepts	Iteration, graphics module/library
Problem Type	Programming problem solving

Cultural Elements	Dress
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Description:

Using the turtle graphics module, write a program to design a citenge. Your program should:

- Colour the graphics background with an appropriate colour
- Include a design of reasonable complexity
- Repeat the design several times across the citenge with a loop

You should consider writing a function to draw the design, given the coordinates to place it. Then you should consider how to loop your program so that it can draw the design in several “rows” and “columns” of the citenge.

Create a random meal generator

CS1 LOs	Develop programs that use the fundamental programming constructs: assignment and expressions, basic I/O, conditional and iterative statements. Develop programs that effectively use the different structured data types provided in the language like arrays/lists, dictionaries, and sets.
CS Concepts	Built-in data structures
Problem Type	Programming problem solving
Cultural Elements	Cuisine

Description:

Write a program to randomly generate a meal. Your meal must contain one element from each of the following:

- A carbohydrate, e.g. nshima, rice or maize
- A vegetable, e.g. ifisashi, rape or cabbage
- A meat, e.g. kapenta, chikanda or beef

You should use a data structure of your choice to store the meal components.

Create a command line provincial information programme

CS1 LOs	Develop programs that use the fundamental programming constructs: assignment and expressions, basic I/O, conditional and iterative statements. Develop programs that effectively use the different structured data types provided in the language like arrays/lists, dictionaries, and sets.
CS Concepts	Built-in data structures, basic I/O, conditionals, looping

Problem Type	Programming problem solving
Cultural Elements	Governance

Description:

Write an information program which can:

- List the 10 provinces of Zambia
- Take input from the user to indicate a province and return the provincial capital and the primary language spoken in the province
- Provide a meaningful error message to the user if they indicate a province which does not exist
- Keep displaying the menu to the user until they indicate that they would like to close the program.

Your program should also use a data structure of your choice to store the information on each province (i.e., do not just hard-code the capitals and languages into variables).

Ghana

Is AFCON this year?

CS1 LOs	Develop programs that use the fundamental programming constructs: assignment and expressions, basic I/O, conditional and iterative statements. Develop programs using functions with parameter passing.
CS Concepts	Functions with parameters, conditionals
Problem Type	Programming problem solving
Cultural Elements	Game

Description:

The African Cup of Nations (AFCON) is the main international men's association football competition in Africa (see https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Africa_Cup_of_Nations). It was first held in 1957, and was subsequently held in 1959, 1962, 1963, 1965, and 1968. Since 1968, it has been held every two years, switching to odd-numbered years in 2013. (So, the tournament was held in both 2012 and 2013)

Write a function that takes the year as a parameter and returns a boolean indicating whether or not the African Cup of Nations was/will be held in that year.

Model Solution (Java):

```
public static boolean isAFCONYear(int year){
    if (year >= 2013 && year%2 == 1)
        return true;
    else if (year >= 1968 && year%2 == 0)
        return true;
    else if (year == 1957 || year == 1959 || year == 1962 || year == 1963
        || year == 1965)
        return true;
    else
        return false;
}
```

Simulate the Kpanlogo dance

CS1 LOs	Develop programs that use the fundamental programming constructs: assignment and expressions, basic I/O, conditional and iterative statements.
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CS Concepts	Iteration
Problem Type	Programming problem solving
Cultural Elements	Dance

Description:

Kpanlogo is a traditional dance from the Ga ethnic group in Ghana. You can watch an example of the dance here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RXubcxknpzY>

You can see that the dance is performed in phases, where each phase involves repeating a given movement pattern a number of times. Assume we have functions that perform some of the basic foot movements of Kpanlogo:

- Functions to step forward/in place with each foot: `leftFootStep()`, `rightFootStep()`
- Functions to shake each foot: `leftFootShake()`, `rightFootShake()`
- Functions to step sideways with each foot: `leftFootSide()`, `rightFootSide()`

Write a programme that uses loops to perform the foot movements of the first four phases of the Kpanlogo dance. You can assume that each phase involves 10 repetitions of the movement pattern for that phase, but write your code such that this number can be easily changed.

Model Solution (Python):

```
numItersPhase1 = 10
for i in range numItersPhase1:
    leftFootStep()
    leftFootStep()
    rightFootStep()
    rightFootStep()

numItersPhase2 = 10
for i in range numItersPhase2:
    leftFootShake()
    rightFootShake()

numItersPhase3 = 10
for i in range numItersPhase3:
    leftFootStep()
    leftFootShake()
    rightFootShake()

numItersPhase4 = 10
for i in range numItersPhase4:
    leftFootSide()
    rightFootSide()
```

Design a class to model a tro-tro

CS1 LOs	Develop programs that effectively use the different structured data types provided in the language like arrays/lists, dictionaries, and sets. Develop programs that create simple classes and instantiate objects of those classes
CS Concepts	Object orientation
Problem Type	Programming problem solving
Cultural Elements	Lifestyle/Transportation

Description:

Design a class to model a “tro-tro”, which is a mini-bus used for shared transportation in Ghana. Similar systems are used in several African countries. You may read about the tro-tro system here (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tro_tro). Every tro-tro has a driver and a driver’s mate/conductor. The tro-tro starts at a home station, and plies a fixed route to its destination, at which point it turns around and returns to its home station. Passengers may get off and join the tro-tro at a number of different stops along the route. The route has a fixed fare, but passengers that join or get off at intermediate stops may pay a reduced fare.

Your class should have the following instance variables:

- Name of driver
- Name of driver’s mate/conductor
- Name of the tro-tro’s home station
- Name of the route that is plied
- List/array of stops along the route
- Passenger capacity of the tro-tro
- Current number of passengers on the tro-tro.
- Current direction of travel of the tro-tro (inbound or outbound)
- Current location/stop of the tro-tro
- Information about the full fare to be paid for the full route as well as reduced fares for shorter journeys.

Think carefully about the data types for each of your instance variables.

You should implement relevant constructors, accessor methods and mutator methods as needed for your class. Note that you may not want to have accessor or mutator methods for all instance variables of your class. Justify your choices. In addition, justify your choice of parameters for the constructors of the class.

Implement the following additional methods of the class:

- A method that allows a passenger to join the tro-tro at a given stop (including the home station), assuming the tro-tro has available space.

- A method that allows a passenger to get off the tro-tro at a given stop
- A method that computes the fare for a passenger, given where they joined and got off the tro-tro.
- A method that allows the mate to compute the change for a given customer, given a payment made.

Write a test program to demonstrate your class, by simulating multiple passengers getting on and off at different stops.

Design a class to play Oware

CS1 LOs	Develop programs that use the fundamental programming constructs: assignment and expressions, basic I/O, conditional and iterative statements. Develop programs using functions with parameter passing. Develop programs that effectively use the different structured data types provided in the language like arrays/lists, dictionaries, and sets. Develop programs that create simple classes and instantiate objects of those classes
CS Concepts	Object orientation
Problem Type	Programming problem solving
Cultural Elements	Games

Description:

Oware is a two-player Ghanaian game in the Mankala family. See the following references to learn about the game and learn how to play the game:

- About Oware: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Oware>
- How to play Oware: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=M3LjiN7BSRs>

In this task, you will write a programme to allow two players to play the game of Oware, virtually. You will define classes to represent:

1. A player
2. An Oware Board
3. The Oware Game

The **Player** class should have instance variables to represent the player names.

The **OwareBoard** class should have a two dimensional array of integers representing the pits and the number of stones in each pit. Each should have a method that plays out a turn starting at a given pit. The numbers in each pit should be adjusted to simulate distributing the stones from one pit to the other pits, following the rules of the game.

The `OwareGame` class should have an oware board and two players. It should also keep track of whose turn it currently is, which pits are “owned” by each player, and the current score. It should have a method to determine when the game is over, and who won.

Write a main method that allows two players to enter their names, and instantiates an `OwareGame` object. Your programme should allow the players to take turns, reading in their desired move and displaying the current state of the board and the current score after each turn. When the game ends or the players wish to stop playing, it should report the winner of the game.